

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Human Reference Atlas (HRA) Editorial Board Procedures

Board Roles and Functions

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Introduction

Human Reference Atlas (HRA) construction and usage requires organizational structures and operating procedures to author, review, approve, and publish diverse digital objects (e.g., [ASCT+B Tables](#), [3D Reference Objects](#), [2D FTU Reference Objects](#)). The development of these HRA organizational structures and procedures is led by a panel of interdisciplinary experts, called the HRA editorial board¹. This Standard Operating Procedure describes how the HRA editorial board functions, including how members are selected, how they ensure data included in the Atlas is of high quality, and what their responsibilities are in terms of guiding the future direction of the HRA.

The primary audience for this SOP is those interested in how the HRA is managed and those considering joining the board. This SOP is general in nature and aims to give an overview of how the editorial board functions.

Roles and Responsibilities

Board Members are subject matter domain experts (SMEs). They are responsible for familiarizing themselves with HRA-related SOPs². They have committed to serving on the HRA editorial board and sharing their expertise in this forum.

The **Principal Investigator (PI)** holds final responsibility for delivering a Human Reference Atlas that satisfies the needs of well-defined user groups (e.g., basic researchers, clinical practitioners, educators and learners). The PI invites and empowers HRA board members, calls and leads HRA board meetings, and ensures timely implementation of decisions made by the board.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Board Member	various	various
Principal Investigator	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu

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Procedures

Key procedures include board member selection, running board meetings, and implementing board member advice and decisions.

Board Selection and Composition

The HRA editorial board is composed of interdisciplinary experts including pathologists, surgeons, and single cell experimentalists.

- Potential board members are nominated by current board members and are voted in by the current board.
- Each board member serves a 2-year term and can opt out earlier if needed.
- Board members can be re-elected to serve additional terms.
- When inviting new members to the board, there is a commitment to building a diverse board.
- Current board members are listed on the HRA portal website at <https://humanatlas.io/editorial-board>.

Board Procedures

- The board meets twice a year, in November and May.
- Efforts will be made to find a time that works for all board members. If a board member cannot attend a meeting s/he is asked to comment on and add to meeting notes via email.
- Key board decisions will be made by consensus through discussion and by vote with a majority present.
- HRA board decisions are communicated to HRA team members by the PI via ASCT+B Working Group meetings.

Board Responsibilities

Board members are expected to share their expertise in the following areas:

- advise on setting HRA editorial policies,
- suggest future HRA extensions (e.g., crosswalks between ASCT+B tables and Azimuth references or OMAPs),
- select organ-specific editors that invite high quality submissions/revisions of HRA digital objects and administer the peer review of submissions,
- optimize incentive structures (e.g., HRA papers in major journals, awards for highest quality contributions by organ teams/editors/reviewers),
- discuss commercial and other means to sustain the HRA effort beyond current NIH funding, and
- act as ambassadors for the HRA—promoting the HRA at relevant conferences and within key communities.

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References and Resources

The below references and resources were used in writing this Standard Operating Procedure.

1. Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center. Human Reference Atlas Editorial Board. <https://humanatlas.io/editorial-board> (2023).
2. Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center. Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures. <https://humanatlas.io/standard-operating-procedures> (2023).

Glossary

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The HRA is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The HRA provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

Principal Investigator (PI): Person who is responsible for the overall conduct of the research at a given site.

Role: One's position on a team.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g., plain English).

Subject Matter Expert (SME): An SME is a person with extensive knowledge about a given topic.

Acknowledgments

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